

SPECIAL FEATURES OF UZBEK DOIRA

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Annotation: The article covers important information about Uzbek doira, its special features and ways of playing it. On the other hand, Information is also provided on the manuals for the circle lessons.

Key words: *musical instrument, dominant players, virtuosity, rhythmic figures, symphonic orchestras, "Chatter", methodological value.*

Music connects the cultures of the world and is a window into the ethos of any country. Likewise, Uzbek music is one of the keys to understanding Uzbek culture. The Uzbek Doyra musical instrument is considered one of the oldest percussion instruments. The doyra drum of Uzbekistan is a traditional musical instrument that can be found in Central Asia. Terracotta monuments found in Central Asia (the city of Nisa, 2nd century BC) depict round women. It is a musical instrument used by Tajik, Uighur, and other eastern peoples. It is a musical instrument used in the ritual ceremonies of the Uzbek people. There are several different versions of this musical instrument in each country. And there are minor differences between them. Some countries call it duff, riq, ghaval, etc., giving it various names. A similar example in Turkey is the "Def" musical instrument. The Uzbek Doyra is one of the most important instruments used in musical performances in Uzbekistan. It was originally played by women at weddings, but by the end of the 18th century, men became the dominant players, and the doyra became a smaller and heavier instrument used for dances. The Uzbek Doyra instrument can even be used as a solo instrument today.

By type this musical instrument is like a tambourine. The instrument of doira is distributed in Central Asia, mainly in Uzbekistan. Uzbek doira consists of a round rib (rim) and a tightly stretched from one side of membrane with a diameter of 360-450 mm. The metal rings are fastened to the rib, the number of which now amounts to 60. Previously, the rib was made from fruit plants - dry grapevine, walnut or beech tree. Now it is made mainly of acacia. The membrane was formerly made from the skin of catfish, goat skin, sometimes the stomach of an animal, now the membrane is made of thick calfskin. Before playing doira it is heated in the sun, by a fire or lamp to increase the tension of the membrane. This contributes to the clarity and sonority of the sound. Metal hoops on the rib contribute to an increase in thermal conductivity when heated. The membrane is so strong that it is able to withstand jumps of a person and knife blow.

Initially, the Uzbek doira was a purely feminine instrument. The women were sitting and playing on doira, as well as Iranian women gathered and played on dafa. In the mountains of the Ferghana Valley, one can see a portrayal of a woman, dated 2000 BC. The woman plays doira accompanied by other women-dancers. Also a statue found by archaeologists dating to 2000 B.C. depicts a woman playing a tambourine, which is similar to doira. Now the skill of playing doira has reached an unprecedented level. In the world such a master of doira as Abos Kasimov from Uzbekistan is well known. Make a travel to Uzbekistan and enjoy playing of Uzbek doira. The sound is extracted by striking of four fingers of both hands (thumbs serve to support the instrument) and palms along the membrane. A blow in the middle of the membrane gives a low and dull sound, a blow near the rib gives a high and ringing sound. To the main sound the ringing of metal pendants joins. The difference in the sound is achieved due to different techniques of the play: finger and palm strokes of different strength, flicks of little fingers (nouhun), gliding of fingers along the membrane, shaking of the instrument, etc. The range of dynamic shades is from a gentle piano to a powerful

forte. The technique of playing doira, developed for centuries, has reached high virtuosity. Uzbek doira is played (by lovers and professionals) solo, accompanying singing and dancing, as well as in ensembles. The doyra's repertoire consists of various rhythmic figures - usuls. In the hands of a virtuoso performing usul, doira can produce gentle sounds resembling a rustle of the wind, or a loud drumbeat, like a spring thunder.

Uzbek Doira is also used in the performance of makoms, mugams. In modern times, doira is often a part of folk, and sometimes symphonic orchestras. The instrument doira is also known as dap and childirma. The Uzbek Doyra musical instrument has a high-pitched tuning system with metal rings. To play the Doyra musical instrument, you hold the edge of the drum with one hand and hit it with both hands using your fingers. They usually tie a piece of string that can be placed around the thumb to help hold the dorara. It is known that the frame part is made of apricot and walnut wood. The outer side of the collar is covered with the tanned skin of a calf, horse, or goat. Inside, there are metal rings similar to those on a tambourine. These rings contribute to the music being played. There are also ringless types of circles. The diameter of the flange is 400–510 mm. In a circle, the sound is made using the fingers of both hands. It is used as an accompaniment in solo performances and in various national musical ensembles. The rhythm units (naqras) used in playing the circle are written in ancient sources. The circle method usually consists of two different strokes. Someone look (baka, bako, bakka, bakko). "Chatter" is the sound it makes when it hits near the edge of a circle. The second shot is an explosion. To move the boom, the fingers are extended and tapped in the middle of the circle.

It should be noted that the study of the performance of the doyra has been covered in many textbooks. Among them are A. Petrosyants "Circle textbook", O. Kamolkhodjayev and A. Liviyev "Circle textbook", I. Ikramov "Circle textbook" and "Etudes for the circle", A. Yuldashev's "Circle colors", O. Kamolkhodjaev

We can mention such textbooks as "Method and melody", I. Ikramov and A. Lutfullayev "Doyra". Admittedly, the information gathered in the literature, the exercises presented, the lessons based on the pedagogical and performance activities of the authors have not lost their methodological value. Therefore, these publications can be recommended to the younger generation of teachers and students. However, in the context of our chosen topic, that is, from the point of view of the subject "Ensemble class", the above literature does not address this issue, so today the creation of textbooks for ensemble class is a matter of urgency. In view of the above, and in particular the need for methodological literature for conducting classes in this area, we have tried to cover in this textbook the issues of the class science of the ensemble of percussion and percussion instruments. It is recommended that students listen to the performance in order to gain a full understanding of the artistic aspects of the work being studied in the classroom. The purpose of the ensemble classes is to help students become more familiar with and listen to world music through their own instruments.

Academic experience shows that, given that the acquisition of theoretical knowledge by students in the study of musical works is one of the necessary requirements, we found it necessary to include in the textbook the following information: a brief introduction to the composer and his work lumot, the main tonality and speed of the work, the description of the musical form, the structural bases of the score, the expressive features of the melodies and important aspects during the performance. That is, the teacher and the student have to find all the necessary information in one place. The knowledge is quickly memorized and assimilated so that participant's can save time and find answers to additional questions in the literature so that they do not have to search. This approach opens up great opportunities for interactive forms in the classroom. Tanbur is a ladomelodic, doyra usul embodiment of Uzbek traditional music. The diversity of functions of the doyra in this area of performance was noted. A special singing

style accompanied by only one doyra in the old school of Bukhara Shashmakom by representatives of this direction, such as Domla Halim, Borukh Zirkiev, Barno Iskhakova and others, will be mentioned. There was talk that the masters of classical music, as a rule, had two doyra with them: a big, soft, matt sounding bam and a relatively small and sonorous zil. Doyra bam corresponded to the slow, contemplative, and doyra zil to the lively and danceable parts of the maqom. And, finally, it was said that, based on the fundamental nature of the usul and the metro rhythm, the masters preferred to teach students first on the doyra, and then introduce them to the tanburu. Another peculiarity of the Fergana style is reflected in the influence of the great singing style. Purely large musical ways of singing are usually manifested by their exception to the accompaniment of the doyra usul, the freedom of the melody weight, and the peculiar murmurs of melancholy moans and melodies. Every young musician should be able to independently analyze the content of the work, its author, listen to the performance from audio and video recordings and compare it with their own performance.

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